

Research Article

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The Negative Effect of Stress at Work Place and its Management

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Abstract Now a days stress is the cronic disease of corporate world due to its negative effect. Because of stress effect not only the employees but also management too. We don't avoid stress because it is a part of everyone's life living in this world. It plays negative marks that have an impact on one's mental and physical well-being. In the field of business, factors leading to work stress on employees performance is vital for any organization to ensure its success and smooth functioning. So many researches have been done in this field but till today we want to know the actual cause and remedy for stress. My aim for this research is understanding the stress and to develop strategies to deal with it. Secondary data from relevant resources have also utilized in this research to reach new findings and process for removing its bad effects. This study suggests many suggestions stress. Demands for the job are main reasons for stress. Work, Life, Balance and Time management are best option for it. In this research best motivation gives both for food practical knowledge.

Keywords Negative effects, work stress, impact balance, time management.

1. Introduction

Stress is a deep feeling of emotional or physical tension. It can come from any thoughts or work which makes us feel frustrated, angry or nervous. Initially stress is a state of worry or mental tension caused by a difficult situation. It is also called as natural human response against opposite situation.

According to topper (2007) and Campbell (2006) started one common definition of stress and explained the aspect of stress like an occurrence of felling out of pressure which happens to a person. The situation, period, level, and consistency of an individual's sentiment are different from person to person. Emotions are used in various forms such as social emotions which states the feeling of an individual like feeling happy, joyous, shame, affection etc. Anybody can be affected by the positive and negative stress initiated from an event. Implication of a significant incident like winning a match or a high profile job can cause a positive stress and negative events can have negative effects or can hurt a person's health like losing an important match or fired from a good job can affect a person in a negative way. At the point when individual face various demands from the physical /psycho social environment or outside environment where they are unfit to react effectual an exertion is required to adopt upto circumstance objective of the research :-

It is designed to achieve these objectives:-

- To explore the various causes of stress and their management in organization.
- To identify the various consequences of stress amongst employers.
- To study the concepts of stress and various types of organization stress.
- To suggest effective ways for managing the stress.

2. Intrinsic

Causes and management of stress at work: -

Main courses for work place stress are extremely due to demands faced at work which are different people.

- Role in organization: - when a leader does not have any idea how to do project and how to manage timeline for a particular task Failure of a particular task is the important issue.
- Career development: - Job insecurity, working hours, control at work and managerial style are main causes for stress.
- Relationship at work: - At office fear from top management, Bulling from collogues and seniors can make relationship stress at work.
- Organizational structure and climate: - The culture which is usually known as work culture with social support and enhance employee wellbeing by providing a positive boost environment for employees who suffer from work.
- Essentials to job: - everyday little stress prompting boredom democracy and frustration work under load. NO work at all may prompt hypo stress in certain situations.

3. Negative effects of stress

When humans face a partly physical response. The body activates resources that help people either stay and confront the challenge or get to safety and fast as possible.

The body produces larger Quantities of the chemicals like cortisol, epinephrine and norepinephrine.

These are the following physical reactions

- Increased blood pressure
- Heightened muscle preparations
- Sweating
- Alertness
- Blood pressure and pulse rise
- Breathing speeds up
- Digestive system slows down
- Immune activity decreases

- Muscles become more tense
- Sleepiness decreases
- Heightened state of alertness.

An individual who feels as though they do not have enough resources to cope will probably have a stronger reaction that could trigger health problems. It effects individuals in different ways.

4. Positive effects of stress

- Some experiences that people generally consider to be positive can lead to stress. Such as having a baby, going on vacation, moving to better home and getting a promotion at work.
- A person may look forward to an increased salary following a promotion for example, but wonder whether they can handle the extra responsibilities. When a person has more difficult challenges, they find their possible ways to get out of the situation.

5. Different types of stress

There are two types of stress:-

- I. Acute stress: - This is also called short type stress usually the more common form of stress. It is related to pressure of events that have recently occurred or faced upcoming challenges in the in future

Acute stressors are often new and tend to have a clear and immediate solution. Acute stress does not cause the same amount of damage as long term but includes short term effects like headaches and upset stomach.

- II. Chronic stress: - Repeated instances of acute stress over an extended period can become chronic and harmful. Chronic stress makes it difficult for the body to return to a normal level of stress hormone activity. A person's body effects by these decreases:-

- Cardiovascular
- Respiratory
- Sleep
- Immune
- Reproductive
- Depression
- Anxiety

Such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) can develop when stress becomes chronic.

Chronic stress can continue unnoticed as people can become used to feeling agitated and hopeless. They are at risk of having a final break down that can lead to suicide.

Common major life events that can trigger stress include:

- Job issues or retirement □ Lack of money or money
- Family problems
- Illness
- Moving home
- Uncertainly or waiting for an important outcome

6. Stress management strategies

Those who work in stressful jobs, such as the military or the emergency services, will have a debriefing session following a major incident and occupational healthcare service will monitor them.

- An online service created to help employees with their mental health. They can find support for their mental health from a licensed therapist.
- People may fixed that there lifestyle measure can help them manage or prevent stream:-
 - i. Exercise
 - ii. Reducing the intake of alcohol, drugs and caffeine
 - iii. Nutrition.
 - iv. Priority management
 - v. Time

- vi. Breathing and relaxation
 - vii. Talking
 - viii. Acknowledging the signs
- Those who often feel as though they do not have the time or energy for hobbies should try some enjoyable new activity that make them feel good. People can turn to their support network if they need ideas.
 - People who fixed that stress is affecting their daily life should seek professional help.
 - Speaking to friends and family.

7. Conclusion

This research study was aimed to study the negative effects of stress and its management. From the above discussion, it can be concluded that stress plays an important role in any organization. The various effects of workplace stress like physical problems, mental disturbance and behavioral problems lead to disturb the climate of the organization. These issues create interpersonal conflicts, decreased productivity, low organizational commitment. etc. By facilitating the employees with effective training the management can provide them with platform to solve their stress related problems. These simple steps can pave the path for improve efficiently of employees and increased productivity of organization.

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